

Four new stilbenoids from the orchids *Coelogyne ochracea* and *Coelogyne cristata*[†]

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Abstract : The orchid *Coelogyne ochracea* Lindl. was earlier chemically investigated by two Indian groups of workers who reported the isolation of six new stilbenoids, viz. coelonin [2,7-dihydroxy-4-methoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene], ochrolide, ochrone A, ochrone B, ochrolic acid and ochrolone, besides the known stilbenoids batatasin-III, coelogin, coeloginin and flaccidin. Further chemical investigation of this orchid by the present investigators has resulted in the isolation of yet two new stilbenoids, designated ochracinone and ochracinanthrone, besides 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde and four known stilbenoids, other than those reported earlier, viz. batatasin-III-dimethylether, flavidin, oxoflavin and flavanthrin. The orchid *Coelogyne cristata* Lindl. was also earlier chemically investigated in our laboratory yielding the first pair of 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyran and pyrone, coelogin and coeloginin, and later two new phenanthrene derivatives coeloginanthrin and coeloginanthridin. Further investigation of this orchid by the present investigators afforded yet two new stilbenoids, designated coeloginone and coeloginanthrone. The structures of the four new stilbenoids ochracinone, ochracinanthrone, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone were established as 6-hydroxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one, 6-hydroxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one, 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one and 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one, respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. Detailed 2D NMR [1-bond ¹H-¹³C (HMQC) and 2- and 3-bond ¹H-¹³C (HMBC) correlations] spectral studies carried out on coeloginone established unambiguous assignments of all the carbon resonances of the compound and partly those of its other three congeners.

Keywords : *Coelogyne ochracea*, *Coelogyne cristata*, Orchidaceae, ochracinone, ochracinanthrone, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone, phenanthropyrone derivatives.

Introduction

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids, viz. stilbene¹, bibenzyls², phenanthrenes and 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes^{3,4} and their dimers⁵⁻⁹, phenanthropyrans and pyrones and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives¹⁰⁻¹⁵, fluorenones¹⁶ and a few other polyphenolics^{17,18}, several triterpenoids¹⁹⁻²¹, steroids of biogenetic importance²²⁻²⁴ and some simple aromatic compounds²⁵. As part of this general programme of research we earlier chemically investigated the orchids *Coelogyne ochracea* and *Coelogyne cristata*. From *C. ochracea* we reported the isolation of a new 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative coelonin (1a)⁴. Later Rao *et al.*²⁶⁻²⁹ also made an extensive chemical investigation of this orchid and isolated five new stilbenoids, viz. ochrolide (2a)²⁶, ochrone A (3a)²⁷,

ochrone B (3b)²⁷, ochrolic acid (1b)²⁸, ochrolone (4)²⁹, besides the known stilbenoids batatasin-III (5a)³⁰, coelonin (1a)⁴, coelogin (2c)¹⁰ and coeloginin (2d)¹⁰ and flaccidin (2f)¹³. Further chemical investigation of this orchid has now resulted in the isolation of yet two new stilbenoids, designated ochracinone and ochracinanthrone, besides 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde and four known stilbenoids, viz. batatasin-III-dimethylether (5b)³¹, flavidin (2k)³², oxoflavin (2l)³³ and flavanthrin (6)⁷. The orchid *C. cristata* was also first chemically investigated in our laboratory resulting in the isolation of the first pair of naturally occurring 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyran and pyrone coelogin (2c)¹⁰ and coeloginin (2d)¹⁰ and later two new phenanthrene derivatives coeloginanthrin (1c)³ and coeloginanthridin (1d)³. Further chemical investigation of this orchid has now yielded yet two more new stilbenoids coeloginone and coeloginanthrone. The structures of

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

ochracinone, ochracinanthrone, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone were established as 6-hydroxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**7a**), 6-hydroxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**7b**), 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**8a**) and 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**8b**), respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. Detailed 2D NMR [1-bond ^1H - ^{13}C (HMQC) and 2- and 3-bond ^1H - ^{13}C (HMBC)] correlation spectral studies were carried on coeloginone (**8a**), which established unambiguous assignments of all the carbon resonances of the compound and partly those of its other three congeners.

Results and discussion

Ochracinone (**7a**), m.p. 145°C, ochracinanthrone (**7b**), amorph. powder, coeloginone (**8a**), m.p. 136°C and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), m.p. 164°C, analysed for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$, $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ and $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$, respectively, which were confirmed by their respective mass spectrometrically derived molecular weights 328, 326, 342 and 340. Ochracinone (**7a**) and coeloginone (**8a**) showed UV absorptions [**7a** : λ_{max} (EtOH) 207.5, 251, 287 and 360 nm (log ϵ 4.02, 4.04, 3.58 and 3.52); **8a** : λ_{max} (EtOH) 228, 230 (sh), 252, 286.5 and 350 nm (log ϵ 4.41, 4.41, 4.47, 4.14 and 3.96)] which are typical of 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene derivatives^{10,33} indicating the presence of an identical chromophoric system **A** in both the compounds. Ochracinanthrone (**7b**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), on the other hand, exhibited entirely different UV absorptions [**7b** : λ_{max} (EtOH) 220, 251, 263.5, 284 and 381 nm (log ϵ 4.05, 3.98, 3.97, 3.78 and 3.34); **8b** : λ_{max} (EtOH) 222, 250, 264, 285 and 383 nm (log ϵ 4.07, 3.99, 3.97, 3.79 and 3.35)] which showed striking resemblance to those of fully aromatic phenanthropyrene derivatives^{13,26,34,35} suggesting the presence of the chromophoric system **B** in both the compounds.

This, in turn, suggests that while ochracinanthrone and coeloginanthrone possess a basic phenanthropyrene ske-

letal system, their respective congeners ochracinone and coeloginone are the corresponding 9,10-dihydro derivatives.

The phenolic nature of ochracinone (**7a**) and ochracinanthrone (**7b**) was indicated by their characteristic colour reactions, alkali-induced bathochromic shifts of the UV maxima [**7a** : λ_{max} (0.1 *M* NaOH-EtOH) 210.5, 250.5, 290 (sh) and 385 nm (log ϵ 4.17, 4.06, 3.55 and 3.57); **7b** : λ_{max} (0.1 *M* NaOH-EtOH) 223, 270, 287 and 394 nm (log ϵ 4.13, 4.11, 3.99 and 3.67)], solubility tests and by their IR spectra exhibiting bands for hydroxyl group(s) [**7a** : ν_{max} 3380–3500 cm^{-1} ; **7b** : ν_{max} 3310 cm^{-1}]. Coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), on the other hand, showed no such band in the above regions suggesting their neutral character. The IR spectra of ochracinone, ochracinanthrone, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone are characterized by the presence of intense bands at ν_{max} 1665, 1660, 1725 and 1728 cm^{-1} , respectively, which may be attributed to absorptions due to δ -lactone carbonyl functions (pyrone system) assumed to be present in their molecules from their UV spectral data. The lower frequencies of absorptions of the above carbonyl groups in ochracinone and ochracinanthrone suggest the involvement of their above carbonyl groups in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. As expected, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone showed the normal absorption frequencies of the δ -lactone carbonyls. These observations thus suggest the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group at C-6 of the system **A** and **B** of ochracinone and ochracinanthrone, respectively, for such intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the two compounds. Consequently, of the system **A** in coeloginone and that of **B** in coeloginanthrone C-6 must be either unsubstituted or may contain a methoxyl group.

The presence of a single phenolic hydroxyl group in each of ochracinone and ochracinanthrone was confirmed by the formation of their respective monoacetyl derivatives, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ (M^+ at m/z 370) and $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$ (M^+ at m/z 368) with Ac_2O and pyridine. But, as expected, coeloginone and coeloginanthrone did not form any acetyl derivative with Ac_2O and pyridine. The IR spectra of the acetyl derivatives of ochracinone and ochracinanthrone lacked the hydroxyl bands of the respective phenolic compounds and, instead, showed bands for acetate function [ochracinone acetate (**7c**) : ν_{max} 1230 and 1740 cm^{-1} ; ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) : ν_{max} 1270 and 1765 cm^{-1}]. Moreover, the original δ -lactone carbonyl absorptions of

ochracinone ($\nu_{\max}$ 1665 cm^{-1}) and ochracinanthrone ($\nu_{\max}$ 1660 cm^{-1}) were shifted to higher frequencies in the IR spectra of ochracinone acetate ($\nu_{\max}$ 1720 cm^{-1}) and ochracinanthrone acetate ($\nu_{\max}$ 1730 cm^{-1}) due to removal of the chelation effect caused by acetylation of the phenolic hydroxyl functions. Thus it may be concluded that each of the above four natural products possesses a carbonyl function in the form of a δ -lactone bridge linking C-4 and C-5 of their phenanthrene/9,10-dihydrophenanthrene skeletal systems and that while such a δ -lactone carbonyl function in coeloginone and coeloginanthrone has no hydroxyl group at their *ortho*-position (C-6), those of ochracinone and ochracinanthrone must have a hydroxyl group at C-6 to form a strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

More compelling evidence for the structures of ochracinone (**7a**), ochracinanthrone (**7b**), coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) was obtained from their ^1H NMR spectra and those of ochracinone acetate (**7c**) and ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**). Thus, the presence of three aromatic methoxyl groups in **7a**, **7b**, **7c** and **7d** and that for four such groups in **8a** and **8b** were confirmed by their respective ^1H NMR spectra [**7a** : δ 3.86, 3.95 and 4.05 (each 3H, s); **7b** : δ 3.97, 3.98 and 4.25 (each 3H, s); **7c** : δ 3.83, 3.88 and 4.00 (each 3H, s); **7d** : δ 3.98, 3.99 and 4.24 (each 3H, s); **8a** : δ 3.84, 3.96, 4.01 and 4.03 (each 3H, s); **8b** : δ 3.96, 4.03, 4.14 and 4.24 (each 3H, s)]. The presence of a single phenolic hydroxyl group in each of **7a** and **7b** was indicated by the appearance of a one-proton singlet at δ 10.90 and 11.42 (each disappearing on deuterium exchange), respectively, in the spectra of the compounds. The downfield shifts of these signals clearly indicate them to be involved in fairly strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding with a carbonyl function. The presence of a 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene and phenanthropyrene system in ochracinone (**7a**) and ochracinanthrone (**7b**), respectively, indicated by their UV and IR spectral data implies that the aforesaid phenolic hydroxyl group in each of **7a** and **7b** must be at C-6 of these compounds, which is the most suitable position for the phenolic hydroxyl function to form strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the pyrone carbonyl group. The disappearance of these hydroxyl proton signals in the ^1H NMR spectra of ochracinone acetate (**7c**) and ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**), each of which, instead, showed a phenolic acetate methyl signal in the spectra of the compounds [**7c** : δ 2.47 (3H, s); **7d** : δ 2.56 (3H, s)] further confirmed the presence of a phenolic

hydroxyl group in each of **7a** and **7b**. Coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), on the other hand, are devoid of any phenolic hydroxyl group and, instead, each contains one additional aromatic methoxyl function. The appearance of a multiplet at δ 2.99 and δ 3.01–3.06 in the ^1H NMR spectra of ochracinone (**7a**) and ochracinone acetate (**7c**), respectively, is reminiscent of the four benzylic protons of a 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene derivative^{10,33}. The signals at δ 2.97 and 3.02 (each 2H, ill-res. br. signal) in the spectrum of coeloginone (**8a**), likewise, establish identical 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene skeletal system also in **8a**. The spectrum of each of ochracinanthrone (**7b**), ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), on the other hand, showed a pair of doublets [**7b** : δ 7.62 and 8.01 (each 1H, d, J 9.1 Hz); **7d** : δ 7.75 and 8.07 (each 1H, d, J 9.2 Hz); **8b** : δ 7.66 and 8.02 (each 1H, d, J 9.0 Hz)] which are typical of H-9 and H-10 of a phenanthropyrene derivative^{13,26,34,35}. The above ^1H NMR spectral data of **7a**, **7c**, **8a**, **7b**, **7d** and **8b** thus firmly establish that while ochracinone (**7a**) and coeloginone (**8a**) possess a 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene skeletal system, ochracinanthrone (**7b**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) have the fully aromatic phenanthropyrene basic skeleton.

The two aromatic protons of ochracinone (**7a**) appeared as a two-proton broad singlet at δ 6.69 which may be attributed to H-1 and H-3 flanked by a methoxyl group at C-2 of a 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrene derivative³⁵. Interestingly, the above signal is shifted up-field by 0.06 ppm in the spectrum of its acetyl derivative **7c**, in which the above signal appears as an ill-res. broad singlet. The marginal up-field shift of these aromatic protons of **7c** may presumably be due to the removal of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the pyrone carbonyl and the phenolic hydroxyl group at C-6 of **7a**. This is corroborated by the chemical shifts of the two aromatic protons of coeloginone (**8a**), which appear almost at the same positions [δ 6.638 and 6.643 (each 1H, ill-res. br. signal)] as those of the aromatic protons of ochracinone acetate (**7c**). The signals at δ 6.638 and 6.643 of **8a** may thus be assigned to H-1 and H-3 of the compound flanked by a methoxyl function at C-2. Having placed the lone hydroxyl group of ochracinone (**7a**) at C-6 and a methoxyl group at C-2, the remaining two aromatic methoxyl groups of **7a** must be located at C-7 and C-8. Based on the same consideration the four methoxyl groups of coeloginone (**8a**) may be placed at C-2, C-6, C-7 and C-8. Ochracinone and coeloginone may, therefore, be represented as 6-hy-

droxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**7a**) and 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**8a**), respectively. Accordingly, ochracinone acetate may be assigned the structure **7c**.

Now, coming back to ochracinanthrone (**7b**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), which have already been shown to possess a phenanthropyrone skeletal system from the characteristic chemical shifts of their H-9 and H-10, the lowfield signals at δ 8.01 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 8.07 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz) and 8.02 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz) of **7b**, ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and **8b**, respectively, were assigned to their H-9. Such low-field resonances of H-9 of the above compounds compared with their H-10 resonances appearing at relatively higher fields, viz. δ 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 7.75 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz) and 7.66 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), respectively, were attributed to the presence of methoxyl group at C-8 of these compounds. The remaining two aromatic protons of **7b** and **8b** appeared as a pair of doublets in each of these compounds at δ 7.16 and 7.09 (each 1H, d, J 2.26 Hz) and 7.12 and 7.05 (each 1H, d, J 3.0 Hz), respectively, which are strikingly similar to those of H-3 and H-1 of structurally related 2-oxygenated phenanthropyrone derivatives^{13,26,34,35}. The corresponding pair of doublets in the spectrum of ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) appeared at δ 7.17 and 7.09 (each 1H, d, J 2.1 Hz). By analogy with the chemical shifts and splitting patterns of H-3 and H-1 of structurally related phenanthropyrone derivatives^{13,26,34,35}, the signals at δ 7.16, 7.17 and 7.12 of **7b**, **7d** and **8b**, respectively, may be attributed to their respective H-3, while those at δ 7.09, 7.09 and 7.05, respectively, of the compounds may be assigned to their H-1. The methoxyl group at C-2 is flanked by H-1 and H-3 of each compound. Having already placed the lone hydroxyl group in **7b** at C-6 and one methoxyl group at C-2 in both **7b** and **8b**, the remaining two methoxyl groups of the former must be placed at C-7 and C-8 and the remaining three methoxyl groups of the latter have the only options to be located at C-6, C-7 and C-8. The structures of ochracinanthrone and coeloginanthrone are thus established as 6-hydroxy-2,7,8-trimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**7b**) and 2,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**8b**), respectively. Ochracinanthrone acetate may thus be represented by the structure **7d**.

The structures of coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) were further affirmed by the ¹³C NMR spectral data of the compounds and those of ochracinone (**7a**), ochracinanthrone (**7b**) and the congener ochrolide (**2a**) by the ¹³C NMR spectral data of their more soluble acetyl derivatives **7c**, **7d** and **2b**, respectively (Table 1). The structure **2a** for ochrolide was earlier²⁶ proposed only on the basis of its ¹H NMR spectral data. The ¹³C NMR spectral studies of ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) made for the first time by the present investigators further confirmed the assigned structure of ochrolide (**2a**). The ¹³C NMR spectra of the above five compounds **8a**, **8b**, **7c**, **7d** and **2b** thus fully account for all the carbon atoms in the respective compounds. The degree of protonation of each carbon atom of the compounds was confirmed by DEPT experiments and in case of coeloginone (**8a**) was further affirmed by 1-bond ¹H-¹³C-correlations (HMQC) and 2- and 3-bond ¹H-¹³C-correlations (HMBC) [with J_{C-H} parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively] also made for the first time. The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of each compound were made by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally related compounds, viz. coeloginin diacetate (**2e**)¹⁰, flaccidin diacetate (**2g**)¹³, oxoflaccidin diacetate (**2h**)¹³, agrostophyllone acetate (**2i**)³⁵ and agrostophylloxin (**2j**)³⁵ (Table 1) taking into account of the additive parameters of the functional groups³⁶ in the benzenoid compounds.

Thus, the nonprotonated carbon resonances in the region of δ_c 157–158 in the ¹³C NMR spectra of coeloginone (**8a**), coeloginanthrone (**8b**), ochracinone acetate (**7c**), ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) [**8a** : δ_c 157.9; **8b** : δ_c 157.6; **7c** : δ_c 158.0; **7d** : δ_c 157.8; **2b** : δ_c 157.2] are typical of the pyrone carbonyl carbons of the structurally similar compounds like coeloginin diacetate (**2e**)¹⁰, oxoflaccidin diacetate (**2h**)¹³, flaccidin diacetate (**2g**)¹³, agrostophyllone acetate (**2i**)³⁵ and agrostophylloxin (**2j**)³⁵. The virtually identical δ_c values of C-1, C-2, C-3, C-3a, C-10a and C-10b of ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) comprising their ring A carbon atoms with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of agrostophyllone acetate (**2i**) and agrostophylloxin (**2j**) both having a phenanthropyrone structure bearing a methoxyl group at C-2 affirmed the placement of a methoxyl group at C-2 of both **7d** and **8b** also having a phenanthropyrone basic skeletal structure.

- 1a : R¹=R²=R³=R⁵=R⁶=R⁷=H, R⁴ =OMe, 9,10-dihydro-
 1b : R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴ =CO₂H, R⁵ =OH, R⁶ =OMe, R⁷ = Me, 9,10-dehydro-
 1c : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁵=OH, R⁴=R⁶=R⁷=H, 9,10-dehydro-
 1d : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁵=OH, R⁴ =R⁶=R⁷=H, 9,10-dihydro-

- 2a : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁶=OH, R⁴,R⁵ = O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2b : R¹= OMe, R²= Me, R³=R⁶=OAc, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2c : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ = OH, R⁴,R⁵=H₂, 9,10-dihydro-
 2d : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ = OH, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dihydro-
 2e : R¹=OMe, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ =OAc, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dihydro-
 2f : R¹=H, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ = OH, R⁴,R⁵ = O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2g : R¹=H, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ =OAc, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2h : R¹=H, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ = OAc, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dihydro-
 2i : R¹=H, R²=Ac, R³=R⁶=OMe, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2j : R¹=H, R²=Me, R³=R⁶ = OMe, R⁴,R⁵=O, 9,10-dehydro-
 2k : R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=H, R⁶=OH, 9,10-dihydro-
 2l : R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴,R⁵ = O, R⁶=OH, 9,10-dihydro-

- 3a : 9,10-dihydro-
 3b : 9,10-dehydro-

- 5a : R=H
 5b : R=Me

- 7a : R=H, 9,10-dihydro-
 7b : R=H, 9,10-dehydro-
 7c : R=Ac, 9,10-dihydro-
 7d : R=Ac, 9,10-dehydro-

- 8a : 9,10-dihydro-
 8b : 9,10-dehydro-

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of **7c**, **8a**, **7d**, **8b**, **2b**, **2e**, **2h**, **2g**, **2i** and **2j**

Carbon atoms	Chemical shifts ^a (δ_{C} values)									
	7c	8a	7d	8b	2b	2e	2h	2g	2i	2j
C-1	110.6	110.3	104.8	104.7	114.3	116.5	116.9	114.7	104.8	104.4
C-2	161.1	160.9	160.3	159.5	150.5	151.3	149.7	149.8	160.3	159.5
C-3	98.7	98.5	102.0	101.5	107.2	107.5	107.9	107.5	102.0	101.8
C-3a	151.7	151.5	151.4	151.0	150.7	156.1	150.8	151.9	151.5	152.8
C-5	158.0	157.9	157.8	157.6	157.2	157.0	157.6	157.2	158.2	158.1
C-5a	108.3	108.3	108.8	108.5	111.7	108.3	114.7	113.0	108.8	109.3
C-6	145.0	156.4	147.4	151.1	147.2	144.4	150.8	151.6	144.1	152.7
C-7	144.7	145.9	144.0	137.2	144.1	145.6	150.0	150.2	143.6	151.1
C-8	156.3	155.1	154.6	154.2	154.4	150.3	118.7	114.9	127.4	115.3
C-8a	110.6	108.4	112.2	109.5	112.6	112.3	132.2	130.6	125.1	124.3
C-9	20.7	20.5	121.1	121.4	121.3	20.2	27.7	126.5	126.3	126.4
C-10	26.6	26.7	126.1	126.5	126.0	26.1	27.3	126.9	126.4	125.9
C-10a	136.5	136.5	132.4	136.1	136.2	136.2	135.5	136.0	132.8	131.4
C-10b	130.1	120.9	125.5	125.1	131.6	128.7	138.1	128.1	125.1	125.5
C-10c	123.2	129.9	125.9	123.5	125.1	124.2	125.0	126.9	121.9	123.0
ArOMe	55.5	55.4	55.8	55.7	61.2	60.5	56.6	56.6	55.9	55.8
	60.7	61.3	61.6	61.6	61.6	61.1			62.9	56.2
	61.2	60.9	61.7	61.7						62.0
		61.8		62.3						
OAc	169.1	-	168.9	-	168.7	168.5	169.0	169.0	169.3	-
	20.9		20.9	-	20.9	168.8	20.8	169.2		
					20.8	20.5	20.9	20.9	20.7	-
						20.7		21.2		

^aThe spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} = 76.9$ ppm.

Again, the striking resemblance of the δ_{C} values of the above carbon atoms of coelginone (**8a**) and ochracinone acetate (**7c**) with the corresponding carbon atoms of agrostophyllone acetate (**2i**), agrostophylloxin (**2j**), coeloginanthrone (**8b**) and ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) indicate the presence of a methoxyl group also at C-2 of coelginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**). The chemical shifts of the above carbon atoms of **8a**, **8b**, **7c** and **7d** are also comparable with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of **2e**, **2h** and **2g**, the difference being due to the change of substitution at C-2 [methoxy in **8a**, **8b**, **7a** and **7d**; acetoxy in **2e**, **2h** and **2g**]. The essentially identical δ_{C} values of the ring A carbon atoms [C-1, C-2, C-3, C-3a, C-10a and C-10b] of ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) with the corresponding carbon atoms of flaccidin diacetate (**2g**) having an acetoxy group at C-2 of a phenanthropyron derivative also established the presence of an acetoxy group at the same position of **2b** having an identical phenanthropyron basic skeleton.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of ochracinone acetate (**7c**) and coelginone (**8a**) are characterized by the appearance of two methylene carbon signals at δ_{C} 20.7 and 26.6 and 20.5 and 26.7, respectively, which may be attributed to C-9 and C-10. Similarly, the remaining two protonated aromatic carbons of ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**), coeloginanthrone (**8b**) and ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) appearing at δ_{C} 121.1 and 126.1, 121.4 and 126.5 and 121.3 and 126.0, respectively, corresponded to their C-9 and C-10. In the light of the well-documented observations^{5,6,10,37,38} that the presence of a substituent, viz. OMe, OH, OAc, etc. at C-8 of phenanthropyrons/pyrones and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives (C-1 of phenanthrenes and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives) causes an upfield shift of ca. 5–6 ppm of their C-9 (C-10 of phenanthrenes and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives), the upfield carbon resonances at δ_{C} 20.7, 20.5, 121.1, 121.4 and 121.3 of ochracinone acetate (**7c**), coelginone (**8a**), ochracinan-

throne acetate (**7d**), coeloginanthrone (**8b**) and ochrolide diacetate (**2b**), respectively, may thus be assigned to their C-9. Accordingly, the relatively downfield carbon resonances at δ_c 26.6, 26.7, 126.1, 126.5 and 126.0 of **7c**, **8a**, **7d**, **8b** and **2b**, respectively, correspond to their C-10. This, in turn, affirms the placement of a methoxyl group at C-8 in both coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) and a methoxyl or OAc at C-8 of ochracinone acetate (**7c**), ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and ochrolide diacetate (**2b**). The remaining two methoxyl groups of **8a** and **8b** must, therefore, be placed at C-6 and C-7. The chemical shifts of C-5a, C-6, C-7, C-8, C-8a and C-10c of coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) are consistent with the placement of three consecutive methoxyl groups at C-6, C-7 and C-8. The carbon atoms of the above methoxyl groups at C-6, C-7 and C-8 having no *ortho*-hydrogen atoms appeared at relatively downfield positions at *ca.* δ_c 60–62, while that of the methoxyl group at C-2 having two *ortho*-hydrogen atoms resonated at the normal region at *ca.* δ_c 55–56.

The lone acetoxy group in ochracinone acetate (**7c**) and ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) and one of the two acetoxy groups in ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) was placed at C-6 by analogy of the δ_c values of their ring C carbon atoms with those of the carbon atoms of coeloginin diacetate (**2e**). The remaining two methoxyl groups of ochracinone acetate (**7c**), coeloginone (**8a**) and ochrolide diacetate (**2b**) must, therefore, be placed at C-7 and C-8. The structures of ochracinone, coeloginone, ochracinanthrone and coeloginanthrone are thus firmly established as **7a**, **8a**, **7b** and **8b**, respectively.

The assignments of both the proton and carbon resonances of coeloginone (**8a**) was confirmed unambiguously by a detailed 2D NMR spectral [both 1-bond ^1H - ^{13}C (HMQC) and 2- and 3-bond ^1H - ^{13}C (HMBC) correlations] analysis of the compound. The HMQC spectrum (with $J_{\text{C-H}}$ parameter set to 160 Hz) of **8a** showed the following correlations.

The upfield benzylic methylene protons at δ_{H} 2.97 (2H, m) which was assigned to H₂-10 of **8a** showed 1-bond correlation with the methylene carbon signal at δ_c 26.7 which may, therefore, be attributed to C-10, while the relatively lowfield methylene proton signal at δ_{H} 3.02 (2H, m) exhibited a similar 1-bond correlation with the

carbon signal at δ_c 20.5 which had already been assigned to C-9. The proton resonance at δ_{H} 3.02 thus corresponds to H₂-9. The methoxyl protons at δ_{H} 3.84, 3.96, 4.01 and 4.03 (each 3H, s) exhibited 1-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 55.4, 61.3, 61.8 and 60.9, respectively. This would imply that the proton resonance at δ_{H} 3.84 and the carbon resonance at δ_c 55.4 correspond to the methoxyl group at C-2, while the remaining proton and carbon resonances may be attributed to the methoxyl groups at C-6, C-7 and C-8. The aromatic protons appearing at δ_{H} 6.638 and 6.643 (each 1H, ill-res. br. signal) showed 1-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 98.5 and 110.3, respectively, assigned to C-3 and C-1, respectively. The proton resonances at δ_{H} 6.638 and 6.643 may then be attributed to H-3 and H-1, respectively, of coeloginone (**8a**).

More compelling evidence for the correct assignments of the above proton and carbon resonances and those of the nonprotonated carbons of **8a** was provided by the following long-range (2-bond and mostly 3-bond) ^1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectrum of the compound (recorded with $J_{\text{C-H}}$ parameter set to 7 Hz).

The benzylic methylene proton resonance at δ_{H} 2.97 of **8a** assigned to its H₂-10 showed 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 108.4, 120.9 and 110.3, which may, therefore, be attributed to C-8a, C-10b and C-1, respectively, of the compound. The above proton signal also exhibited 2-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_c 136.5 and 20.5, which thus correspond to C-10a and C-9, respectively. The other benzylic methylene proton resonance at δ_{H} 3.02 (H₂-9) exhibited 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 136.5, 129.9 and 155.1, which were thus assigned to C-10a, C-10c and C-8, respectively. The above proton signal also showed 2-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 26.7 and 108.4, which have already been assigned to C-10 and C-8a, respectively.

The aromatic proton at δ_{H} 6.638 (already assigned to H-3) showed 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonance at δ_c 110.3 which has already been assigned to C-1. The above proton also exhibited 2-bond correlations with the carbons resonating at δ_c 151.5 and 160.9, which thus correspond to C-3a and C-2, respectively. The other aromatic proton resonance δ_{H} 6.643 (already assigned to

Fig. 1. 2-bond and 3-bond ^1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited in the HMBC spectrum of coeloginone (8a)

H-1) showed 3-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_{C} 98.5 and 26.7, which may thus be assigned to C-3 and C-10, respectively. The above proton also displayed

a 2-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_{C} 160.9 which has already been assigned to C-2.

The methoxyl proton resonances at δ_{H} 3.84, 3.96.

Scheme 1. Chemical correlation of ochracinone (7a) with coeloginone (8a) and coeloginin (2d) and that of ochracinanthrone (7b) with coeloginanthrone (8b) and ochrolide (2a).

4.01 and 4.03 showed 3-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_c 160.9, 145.9, 155.1 and 156.4, respectively, which may be assigned to C-2, C-7, C-8 and C-6, respectively. The nonprotonated carbon resonances at δ_c 108.3 and 157.9, however, showed no correlation with any proton. The signals at δ_c 108.3 and 157.9 may thus be assigned to C-5a and C-5, respectively.

The above 2- and 3-bond ^1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectrum of coeloginone (**8a**) are shown on its structural diagram (Fig. 1).

Thus, from the above HMQC and HMBC ^1H - ^{13}C correlations of coeloginone (**8a**) unambiguous assignments of both proton and carbon resonances of the compound could be made possible and this has lent credence to the assignments of the proton and carbon resonances of the other three congeners.

The structures of ochracinone (**7a**), coeloginone (**8a**), ochracinanthrone (**7b**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**) are also in conformity with their respective mass spectral fragmentations. Typical of aromatic compounds, the mass spectra of these compounds showed only a few peaks of relatively high intensities. The mass spectra of these compounds are characterized by the elimination of methyl radicals and CO from the resultant ion fragments and also from the pyrone moiety.

The proposed structures of **7a**, **7b**, **8a** and **8b** were finally confirmed by chemical correlations as shown in Scheme 1. Thus, methylation of ochracinone (**7a**) and ochracinanthrone (**7b**) by heating under reflux with MeI in dry acetone over anhydrous K_2CO_3 for 16 h afforded coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), respectively (Scheme 1). Similar methylation of coeloginin (**2d**) and ochrolide (**2a**) under identical reaction conditions gave coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), respectively (Scheme 1).

The structures of ochracinone and coeloginone, and ochracinanthrone and coeloginanthrone are thus firmly established as **7a** and **8a**, and **7b** and **8b**, respectively, and represent two pairs of new additions to the growing list of naturally occurring 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrones and fully aromatic phenanthropyrones, respectively.

Experimental

M.p.s : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). MPLC :

silica gel (230–400 mesh). TLC : silica gel G. IR : KBr discs. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR : 300 and 75 Mz, respectively, CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard. HMQC and HMBC spectra of **8a** were recorded in CDCl_3 in a 500 Mz instrument with $J_{\text{C-H}}$ parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively. MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analyt. samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80°C. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents.

Plant materials :

Coelogyne ochracea Lindl. and *Coelogyne cristata* Lindl. were collected from Kalimpong (Darjeeling, India) in August, 2002. A voucher specimen (Majumder s.n.) of each of the two orchids was deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta (CUB).

Isolation of ochracinone (7a), ochracinanthrone (7b), coeloginone (8a), coeloginanthrone (8b) and other compounds of previously known structures :

Air-dried powdered whole plants of *Coelogyne ochracea* and *Coelogyne cristata* (each 5 kg) were separately kept soaked in MeOH (10 L) for three weeks at room temperature. The MeOH extracts were then separately drained out and concentrated under reduced pressure to ca. 100 ml and diluted with water (500 ml) and the liberated solids were separately extracted with Et_2O . The Et_2O extract in each case was fractionated into acidic and nonacidic fractions with 2 M aq. NaOH. The aqueous alkaline solution in each case was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids in each case were extracted with Et_2O , washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. The acidic and nonacidic residues obtained from both the orchids were separately chromatographed over silica gel. ✓

Chromatography of the acidic fraction of *C. ochracea* :

The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) gave a mixture of ochracinone (**7a**) and ochracinanthrone (**7b**). The above mixture was then subjected to MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) as the solvent system. The early fractions afforded pure ochracinanthrone (**7b**) (0.05 g) as amorph. powder and the later fractions gave ochracinone (**7a**) (0.2 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 145°C.

Ochracinanthrone (**7b**) : (Found : C, 66.23; H, 4.25. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 66.26; H, 4.29%); UV λ_{max} nm : 220, 251, 263.5, 284 and 381 (log ϵ 4.05, 3.98, 3.97, 3.78 and 3.34); λ_{max} (0.1 M NaOH-EtOH) nm : 223, 270, 287 and 394 (log ϵ 4.13, 4.11, 3.99 and 3.67); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3310 (OH), 1660 (chelated δ -lactone $-C=O$), 1466, 1160, 820 and 735 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (300 Mz) : δ 3.97, 3.98 and 4.25 (each 3H, s; 3 $\times$ ArOMe), 7.09 (1H, d, J 2.26 Hz; H-1), 7.16 (1H, d, J 2.26 Hz; H-3), 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz; H-9), 8.01 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz; H-10) and 11.42 (1H, s, disappeared on deuterium exchange; intramolecularly hydrogen bonded ArOH); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 326 [M^+] (100), 311 (51), 283 (38), 254 (20.2), 240 (6.4) and 212 (6.3). Ochracinanthrone (**7b**) was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner to give ochracinanthrone acetate (**7d**) as a semi-solid mass (Found : C, 65.19; H, 4.31. $C_{20}H_{16}O_7$ requires : C, 65.22; H, 4.35%); UV λ_{max} nm : 262, 329, 364.5 and 380 (log ϵ 4.26, 3.58, 3.38 and 3.44); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1270 and 1765 (OAc), 1730 (δ -lactone carbonyl), 1625, 1590, 1460, 1420, 850, 755, 670 and 625 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (300 Mz) : δ 2.56 (3H, s; OAc), 3.98, 3.99 and 4.24 (each 3H, s; 3 $\times$ ArOMe), 7.09 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz; H-1), 7.17 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz; H-3), 7.75 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz; H-9) and 8.07 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz; H-10); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 368 [M^+] (19), 326 (100), 311 (37.2), 283 (25.5), 254 (11.7), 240 (6.3) and 212 (6.4).

Ochracinone (**7a**) : (Found : C, 65.81; H, 4.85. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires : C, 65.85; H, 4.88%); UV λ_{max} nm : 207.5, 251, 287 and 360 (log ϵ 4.02, 4.04, 3.58 and 3.52); λ_{max} (0.1 M NaOH-EtOH) nm : 210.5, 250.5, 290 (sh) and 385 (log ϵ 4.17, 4.06, 3.55 and 3.57); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3380–3500 (OH), 1665 (δ -lactone carbonyl), 1625, 1515, 1535, 1480, 840, 800, 775 and 745 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (300 Mz) : δ 2.99 (4H, m; H_2 -9 and H_2 -10), 3.86, 3.95 and 4.05 (each 3H, s; 3 $\times$ ArOMe), 6.69 (2H, br. s; H-1 and H-3), 10.90 (1H, s, disappeared on deuterium exchange : chelated Ar-OH); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 328 [M^+] (100), 313 (80.8), 285 (23.4), 256 (6.4), 242 (8.5) and 214 (7.4). Ochracinone (**7a**) was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner to give ochracinone acetate (**7c**) as a semi-solid mass (Found : C, 64.83; H, 4.83. $C_{20}H_{18}O_7$ requires : C, 64.86; H, 4.86%); UV λ_{max} nm : 222.5, 247.0, 257.0 and 334.5 (log ϵ 4.52, 4.50, 4.39 and 3.90); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1230 and 1740 (OAc), 1720 (δ -lactone carbonyl), 1640, 1510, 1464,

780 and 675 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (300 Mz) : δ 2.47 (3H, s; OAc), 3.01–3.06 (4H, m; H_2 -9 and H_2 -10), 3.83, 3.88 and 4.00 (each 3H, s; 3 $\times$ ArOMe), 6.63 (2H, ill-res. br. signal; H-1 and H-3); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 370 [M^+] (21), 328 (100), 313 (71), 285 (18), 256 (4), 242 (6.3) and 214 (7.4).

The early fractions of petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) eluate from the main chromatographic column gave a mixture of ochrone A (**3a**) and ochrone B (**3b**). On repeated chromatography, the above mixture yielded, pure ochrone A (0.05 g) in the early fractions, crystallized from benzene, m.p. 255°C and ochrone B (0.05 g), as amorph. powder in the later fractions. Washing the main column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) gave a mixture of batatasin-III (**5a**), flaccidin (**2f**), ochrolone (**4**), ochrolic acid (**1b**), ochrolide (**2a**) and flavidin (**2k**), which on repeated MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) as solvent system yielded, in the early fractions, pure ochrolic acid (**1b**) (0.08 g), crystallized from EtOAc, m.p. 228°C. The later fractions gave a mixture of the remaining five compounds which were finally separated by repeated MPLC [batatasin-III (0.2 g), as a semisolid mass; flaccidin (0.075 g), as a semisolid mass; ochrolone (0.03 g), crystallized from $CHCl_3$, m.p. 212°C; ochrolide (0.04 g), crystallized from benzene, m.p. 209–211°C; flavidin (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 210°C.

Further elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) afforded a mixture of two compounds, which on repeated column chromatography, afforded finally pure coelogenin (**2d**) (0.3 g) in the early fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc as yellowish needles, m.p. 198°C and coelogenin (**2c**) (0.2 g) in the later fractions, crystallized from the same solvent mixture, as colourless needles, m.p. 154°C. The petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate from the main column afforded pure coelonin (**1a**) as an amorph. powder (0.1 g). Further elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) gave oxoflavin (**2l**) (0.2 g) as an amorph. powder, m.p. > 300°C, and the petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate gave flavanthrin (**6**) (0.04 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 285°C. All the above thirteen compounds were identified by direct comparison with their respective authentic samples.

Chromatography of the nonacidic fraction obtained from C. ochracea :

The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate gave a mixture of 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde and batatasin-III

dimethylether (**5b**). The above mixture was then subjected to MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) as the solvent system. The early fractions in the above MPLC gave pure 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.5 g) as a thick liquid, and batatasin-III dimethyl ether (0.05 g) in the later fractions as a semisolid mass. The above two compounds were identified by direct comparison with their respective authentic samples.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from Coelogyne cristata :

The petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) eluate gave a mixture of coelogin (**2c**) and coeloginin (**2d**), which on repeated chromatography finally afforded pure coeloginin (0.3 g) in the early fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc as yellowish needles, m.p. 198°C, and coelogin (0.2 g), in the later fractions, crystallized from the same solvent mixture as colourless needles, m.p. 154°C. Washing the main column with petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) gave a gummy residue comprising mainly two compounds, which was subjected to MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) as the solvent system. The early fractions gave a residue which was identified as coeloginanthridin (**1d**) as the major constituent, while the later fractions gave a mixture containing mostly coeloginanthrin (**1c**). The above two mixtures were again separately subjected to MPLC using the same solvent system to give finally pure coeloginanthridin (**1d**) (0.1 g) and coeloginanthrin (**1c**) (0.2 g) both as semisolid mass. The above compounds were identified by direct comparison with their respective authentic samples.

Chromatography of the nonacidic fraction of C. cristata :

The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate gave a mixture of coeloginone (**8a**) and coeloginanthrone (**8b**), which on MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) as the solvent system gave, in the early fractions, pure coeloginanthrone (0.03 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 164°C. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded coeloginone (0.3 g), also crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 136°C.

Coeloginanthrone (**8b**) : (Found : C, 67.02; H, 4.68. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires : C, 67.06; H, 4.71%); UV λ_{max} nm : 222, 250, 264, 285 and 383 (log ϵ 4.07, 3.99, 3.97, 3.79 and 3.35); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1728 (δ -lactone carbonyl),

1629, 1620, 1465, 820 and 801 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (300 Mz) : δ 3.96, 4.03, 4.14 and 4.24 (each 3H, s; $4 \times ArOMe$), 7.05 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz; H-1), 7.12 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz; H-3), 7.66 (1H, d, J 9 Hz; H-9) and 8.02 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz; H-10); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 340 [M^+] (100), 325 (62.4), 297 (25.8), 269 (20.4) and 254 (17.2). Coeloginone (**8a**) : (Found : C, 66.63; H, 5.22. $C_{19}H_{18}O_6$ requires : C, 66.66; H, 5.26%); UV λ_{max} nm : 228, 230 (sh), 252, 286.5 and 350 (log ϵ 4.41, 4.41, 4.47, 4.14 and 3.96); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1725 (δ -lactone carbonyl), 1598, 1461, 856 and 692 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR (500 Mz) : δ 2.97 and 3.02 (each 2H, ill-res. br. signal: H_2-10 and H_2-9 , respectively), 3.84, 3.96, 4.01 and 4.03 (each 3H, s; $4 \times ArOMe$), 6.638 and 6.643 (each 2H, ill-res. br. signal; H-3 and H-1, respectively); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 342 [M^+] (100), 327 (69), 299 (27.6), 269 (20) and 256 (18).

Methylation of ochracinone (7a), ochracinanthrone (7b), coeloginin (2d) and ochrolide (2a) :

Ochracinone (**7a**), ochracinanthrone (**7b**), coeloginin (**2d**) and ochrolide (**2a**) (each 0.03 g) in dry acetone (25 ml in each case) were separately treated with MeI (1 ml) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (1 g in each case). The mixtures were separately heated under reflux for 16 h. MeI (1 ml) and acetone (10 ml) were added in each case after the reaction proceeded for 8 h. The solution in each case was filtered, washed with acetone and the solvent removed. The residues thus obtained were separately chromatographed. The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the residue obtained in the methylation of ochracinone (**7a**) gave coeloginone (**8a**) (0.025 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 136°C. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded traces of unchanged ochracinone. Similarly, the early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the residue obtained in the methylation of ochracinanthrone (**7b**) afforded coeloginanthrone (**8b**) (0.023 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 164°C. The later fractions of the same eluate gave traces of unchanged ochracinanthrone. Chromatography of the residue obtained in the methylation of coeloginin (**2d**) gave coeloginone (**8a**) (0.025 g), in the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 136°C. Washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) afforded

traces of unchanged coeloginin. Similarly, chromatography of the residue obtained in the methylation of ochrolide (**2a**) gave coeloginanthrone (**8b**) (0.024 g), in the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate, crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p.164°C. Washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) afforded traces of unchanged ochrolide.

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